

Performance Improvement on TCP Gallop Vegas

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Abstract – In this paper, we consider the problem of congestion control and present a new congestion avoidance technique, which improves the throughput of TCP Gallop Vegas. TCP Gallop Vegas provides better performance than TCP Vegas and TCP Reno with respect to overall network utilization, stability, fairness, throughput, packet loss and burstiness. The enhancement on TCP Gallop Vegas introduced in this paper reduces the burstiness, raises the rate to the available bandwidth in shorter time, improves the startup performance and improves the throughput of TCP Gallop Vegas. The phenomenon used in this paper is that throughput of Gallop Vegas can be approximated by a function of round trip time. Our simulation results show that the performance of TCP Gallop Vegas improves significantly in the slow start phase and congestion avoidance phase of the slow start algorithm

Keywords: TCP Vegas, TCP Gallop Vegas, Slow Start and Congestion Avoidance Phase, BaseRTT, Actual RTT, Congestion window Size.

I. Introduction

Computer networks have experienced an explosive growth over the past few years resulting in severe congestion problems. In order to avoid it, TCP congestion control is designed for network stability, robustness and opportunistic used of network buffer and bandwidth resources on an end- to-end per connection basis. Congestion control consists of two components 1) Source algorithm implemented in TCP that adapts sending rate or window size, 2) Link algorithm implemented in routers that updates and feed backs the local congestion information to sources. Different protocols used for source algorithm and link algorithm uses different metrics as congestion measures. The slow start algorithm consists of four phases named slow start phase, congestion avoidance phase, fast recovery phase and fast transmit phase. The modification on slow start phase of TCP Vegas results in TCP Gallop Vegas, which has the better performance than the TCP Vegas.

TCP Reno uses loss probability as congestion measure and TCP vegas primarily uses queuing delay as congestion measure [2]. TCP Gallop Vegas uses the transmission rate as congestion measure so that it raises the transmission rate to the available bandwidth resulting in improved sender's throughput. The experimental studies presented in [1] have shown that the TCP Gallop Vegas as a delay based congestion strategy achieves a better performance in comparison with TCP Vegas.

In the present work, an enhancement on TCP Gallop Vegas is proposed, which uses the round trip time as a

metric for congestion control. The actual round trip time is taken into account, which is used for controlling the transmission rate resulting in the better performance than the TCP Gallop Vegas.

II. Related Work

TCP Vegas uses the difference in the expected and actual flow rates to estimate the available bandwidth of the network. The difference in flow rates is calculated as
Diff = Expected Rate – Actual Rate
= $W/d - W/D$ where W be the congestion window size, d be the minimum observed RTT ie Base RTT and D be the actual RTT.

The estimated backlog of packets in the network queue is computed as

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= (\text{Expected Rate} - \text{Actual Rate}) \times \text{Base RTT} \\ &= (W/d - W/D) \times d \\ &= W(D - d)/D\end{aligned}$$

Vegas doubles the congestion window size only every other RTT. In addition, every other RTT, Vegas calculate the difference in the flow rate (Diff) and Δ . When $\Delta > \gamma$ (whose_default is 1) vegas leaves the slow start phase, decreases its congestion window size by 1/8 and enters the congestion avoidance phase. Vegas doubles it's sending rate in short interval, which results in Δ bias. Therefore, the congestion window size increases too quickly in the slow start phase resulting in long congestion avoidance phase.

Vegas sends two packets when it receives one acknowledgement. It may cause bursty traffic if lot of acknowledgements return to the sender consecutively. Gallop vegas sends one packet when it receives one acknowledgement when it sends an extra packet to increase the congestion window size after getting two or

more acknowledgement. Gallop vegas do not increase the congestion window size in the first RTT which is either the beginning of the start or after the retransmission timeout because the sender does not have any idea about this connection. After the second RTT, Gallop vegas starts to increase the congestion window with a rate between exponential growth and linear growth. It results in more efficiency comparing to vegas.

TCP Gallop Vegas raises the transmission rate in the slow start phase. It results in reducing the time taken to reach the available bandwidth. Therefore the ultimate aim of TCP Gallop Vegas is to minimize the long congestion avoidance phase of TCP Vegas. The primary aim of this paper is to minimize the long congestion avoidance phase considerably lesser than the TCP Gallop Vegas and reduce the time taken to reach the available bandwidth in slow start phase. The modification to the slow start phase is proposed using the round trip time as congestion measure, which minimize the congestion avoidance phase considerably. The BaseRTT and actual RTT are considered in this paper, which improves the sender's throughput of TCP Gallop Vegas significantly.

Slow Start Mechanism of TCP Gallop Vegas

In Gallop Vegas, the congestion window size is not increased in the first RTT which is either the beginning of the start or after a retransmission timeout. After the second RTT, the congestion window size is increased with a rate between exponential growth and linear growth [1]. It results in that the congestion window size increases too quickly. Next the delta ((expected – actual) * BaseRTT) is recalculated which increases the congestion window with stable growth. It avoids the congestion avoidance phase too early and reduces the traffic burstiness in the network.. The values, state and corresponding motivation at last RTT is tabulated below.

Value	State	Corresponding motivation at last RTT
0	$\Delta < \gamma$ $\gamma \leq \Delta < \beta$	'incr' is increased by one. Do not do any action
1	$\gamma \leq \Delta < \beta$	'incr' is decreased by one half.
2	$\beta < \Delta$	The congestion window size is decreased by the sum of 'incr' and surplus of queue ($\Delta - \beta$)

III. Proposed System

Gallop Vegas introduced a concept of stable growth in the slow start mechanism which uses the congestion window size in between the linear and exponential growth. The Gallop Vegas uses the BaseRTT for delta

calculation. To improve the performance of the Gallop Vegas, the actual RTT is used instead of BaseRTT in the calculation of delta. The performance is improved with single sender in one network as shown in the Fig 1. While applying the backward traffic (multiple sender in one network as shown in Fig 2), the proposed algorithm improves the performance of Gallop Vegas in slow start phase and congestion avoidance phase. In the proposed algorithm uses the BaseRTT to calculate the delta the beginning of the slow start phase, which decides the congestion window size. Next the recent RTT is considered and used to calculate the delta, which decides the congestion window size in further transmission. The delta value is calculated from the formula

$$\text{Delta} = (\text{expected} - \text{actual}) * \text{RTT}.$$

IV. Simulation and Performance Analysis

The simulation experiments are conducted using Ns-2 version 2.29. We uses two types of topology, single sender without backward traffic and multiple senders with backward traffic.

Single Sender without Backward Traffic

The simulation network topology of one single link is shown in Fig 1 where S1 represents a sender host and D1 represents a destination host. R1 and R2 represent two finite buffer gate ways. The propagation delay is set to 1ms between the node to router and 48ms between the router to router.

Fig. 1 Single sender without back traffic

Multiple Sender with Backward Traffic

The simulation network topology of multiple links is shown in Fig 2 where S1 and S2 represent the sender hosts and D1 and D2 represent the destination host. R1 and R2 represent two finite buffer gate ways and the time delay is 1 ms and 48 ms between node to router and router to router respectively.

Fig 2 Multiple senders with backward traffic

There is no significant improvement obtained if the single sender topology is used. The throughput is same as

the gallop vegas. If the proposed algorithm is used in multiple senders with backward traffic, then a significant improvement in the throughput is obtained. We first simulated the TCP and then TCP gallop vegas. The throughput of TCP gallop vegas is improved than the TCP vegas. The modified gallop vegas also shows a better improvement in the throughput while applying the proposed algorithm in the multiple sender with backward traffic. Fig 3 shows the throughput of TCP and TCP gallop vegas respectively. This simulation result is obtained by using the single sender without backward traffic. In Fig 3 of TCP vegas, at 1.4 seconds it reaches congestion avoidance phase and leads to linear growth. In TCP Gallop Vegas, it doesn't reach congestion avoidance phase like TCP Vegas. It remains in slow start phase and increase the throughput.

Fig. 3 Throughput of TCP Vegas and TCP Gallop Vegas without backward traffic

Fig 4 shows the comparison of throughput of TCP Gallop vegas and Modified Gallop vegas. This simulation results are obtained by applying the proposed algorithm in the multiple sender with backward traffic. Throughput of TCP gallop vegas is reduced when it reaches to 330×10^6 due to backward traffic. But in case of modified TCP gallop vegas, the throughput is reduced when it reaches to 350×10^6 .

Fig. 5 Throughput of TCP Gallop Vegas and Modified Gallop Vegas

V. Conclusion and Future Work

The Modified TCP gallop vegas simulation results showed that the performance is improved while applying the algorithm in the backward traffic network. The RTT

depends on traffic from other sources, data rate and cumulative acknowledgement. This criteria leads to unstable environment. The throughput of TCP gallop vegas is improved but the stability in the slow start phase is fluctuated. In future, it can be stabilized in the multiple senders with backward traffic environment.

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